

STUDYING THE FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF CHROMOSOMAL ABNORMALITIES AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH DRIVER SOMATIC MUTATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE MYELOID LEUKEMIA

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Abstract. *The given article presents the peripheral blood of 145 patients with AML, who were in inpatient treatment at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan served as the material for molecular genetic research. Clinical and laboratory studies were performed at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

The study demonstrated a significantly higher frequency of NPM1 mutation distribution in patients with normal karyotypes compared to patients with chromosomal disorders (35.3% versus 9.4% with $\chi^2=7.0$; OR=0.2; $p=0.01$; 95% CI: 0.06-0.65).

Statistical processing of the results was performed using the standard Open Epi V.9.2 application software package.

Keywords: *mutation, genetic marker NPM1, hemorrhage, thrombocytopenia, blast cells.*

Relevance of the problem. It is important to suggest that acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a clonal malignant disease characterized by ineffective hematopoiesis. Most AML patients have various cytogenetic and molecular genetic lesions, which are combined with certain biological and clinical features of the disease [3,7,8]. Approximately 50–60% of patients with de novo and 80–95% of patients with secondary AML have chromosomal changes. It should be noted that structural cytogenetic aberrations are the most common markers and occur in approximately 40% of cases of de novo AML. A fairly large group of patients with a normal karyotype (NC-AML), formally classified as intermediate risk, is extremely heterogeneous in terms of the prognosis of the disease course. Current prognostic classifications of AML today include only some mutations characterized by known prognostic significance, in particular t(8;21), NPM1 and BRAF [6,9,10].

Definitely, classical karyotype analysis allows to detect chromosomal changes in approximately half of AML patients. Many chromosomal aberrations are independent prognostic factors and are included in the current classification of AML published by the World Health Organization (WHO) [5]. Patients with a normal karyotype (NK), according to the international classification, belong to the intermediate risk group. However, it is well known that the clinical picture and prognosis of the disease in this group of patients can be very different. Identification of mutations in patients with NK allows not only to identify categories of patients with a certain prognosis, but also to understand the molecular pathogenesis of the disease. More than 85% of NK-AML patients have genome mutations [1,4]. Some of these mutations not only supplement prognostic information, but also are a potential basis for the development of new targeted therapy options. Although some mutations are already included in the current type of classification and

recommendations of European experts, a more detailed study of the molecular architecture of leukemia is necessary [2, 11].

Material and methods of the study. The material for the molecular genetic study was the peripheral blood of 145 patients with AML who were inpatient treatment at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Clinical and laboratory studies were performed at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Besides that, in the main study group of patients, the median age was 44.6 ± 1.2 years. In particular, in male patients, the average age was 47.2 ± 1.9 years, in female patients - the median age was 42.2 ± 1.5 years. The median age was higher in men than in women.

Mutation testing was performed on the Rotor-Gene Q device (Quagen, Germany), using a commercial test kit from Syntol LLC (Russia).

Statistical processing of the results was performed using the standard Open Epi V.9.2 software package.

Results and discussion. While researching it was found out that karyotyping of cells was performed in 83 patients out of 145 examined patients. In accordance with the objectives of the study, we performed a karyotype analysis using the standard cytogenetic study (SCS) method in patients with AML.

However, during the standard cytogenetic study, karyotype changes were detected in 32 patients out of 83 (38.6%) patients, while in 51 patients (61.4%) chromosomal aberrations were not detected (karyotype 46XX or 46XY).

In male patients, chromosomal abnormalities were found in 19 out of 39 (48.7%) patients, and no karyotype abnormalities were detected in 20 patients (51.3%). In the group of female patients, chromosomal aberrations were detected in 13 of 44 (29.5%) patients, and in 31 patients (70.5%) no karyotype changes were detected. Chromosomal aberrations were registered more often among men compared to women. In young patients, karyotype abnormalities were detected in 33.3% of cases (22 of 66), normal karyotype was detected in 66.7% (44 of 66) patients, respectively. In elderly patients, chromosomal abnormalities were registered in 10 of 17 patients (58.8%), normal karyotype was detected in 7 of 17 patients (41.2%). Thus, chromosomal aberrations were registered more often among men and in elderly patients.

During the study period, t(8;21) mutations were detected in 9.7% (14 of 145) of patients, however, mutation of this gene was not detected in 90.3% of cases, respectively. In 5 of 14 (35.7%) patients, only single mutations were detected. In 9 of 14 (64.3%) patients, mutations were combined. Mutations of this genetic marker were statistically insignificantly more often detected in patients with an altered karyotype – in 6 (18.8%) of 32 examined patients compared to patients without it ($\chi^2=0.1$; OR=1.2; $p=0.7$; 95%CI:0.39–3.98). In the group of patients with a favorable karyotype, t(8;21) mutations were detected only in 15.7% of patients (see Table 1).

Additionally, mutations in the inv(16;9) gene were detected in 4 (2.8%) of 145 patients with AML. This mutation was not registered in 141 (97.2%) of 145. In all cases, the mutation of the above-mentioned gene was combined. While studying patients depending on the karyotype, it was found that the highest detection of mutations in the inv(16, 9) gene was detected in the group of patients with a normal karyotype - in 3 (5.9%) of 51 patients. In the group of patients with

chromosomal aberrations, the incidence of mutation of the studied gene was found in 1 of 32 patients (3.1%).

Table 1

Differences in the frequency of the *t(8, 21)* gene mutation factor in groups of patients with normal and altered karyotypes

Factor	Number of examined				χ^2	p	OR	95%CI
	Altered karyotype		Normal karyotype					
	n	%	n	%				
exists	6	18.8	8	15.7	0.1	p = 0.7	1.2	0.39 – 3.98
doesn't exist	26	81.2	43	84.3	0.1	p = 0.7	0.8	0.25 – 2.59

Despite this, the differences in the frequency of occurrence of the *inv* gene mutation (16, 9) in patients with a normal karyotype and with an altered karyotype were not statistically significant ($\chi^2=0.3$; OR=0.5; p=0.6; 95% CI:0.05–5).

The presence of mutations of the genetic marker BRAF was statistically significantly associated in patients with chromosomal aberrations in relation to patients with a normal karyotype (12.5% versus 2.0%). In the presence of this mutation, the risk of developing chromosomal abnormalities is significantly higher (7.1 times) compared to patients without a mutation of this gene ($\chi^2=3.9$; OR=7.1; p=0.05; 95% CI:1–50.81) (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution frequency of the genetic marker BRAF and its relationship with chromosomal abnormalities in patients with AML.

Altered karyotype, Normal karyotype, BRAF gene mutation

In the study, mutations in the NPM1 gene were detected in 17.2% of patients, and in 82.8% of cases this mutation was not registered. In 16 of 25 patients, single mutations of the NPM1 gene were detected. In the remaining 9 patients out of 25, combined mutations were registered.

The study demonstrated a significantly higher frequency of distribution of NPM1 mutations in patients with a normal karyotype compared to patients with chromosomal abnormalities (35.3% versus 9.4% at $\chi^2=7.0$; OR=0.2; p=0.01; 95% CI:0.06–0.65).

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that during the study of standard cytogenetic, karyotype changes were detected in 38.6% of patients, while chromosomal aberrations were not detected in 61.4% of cases. Chromosomal aberrations were registered more frequently among men and in elderly patients. In patients with normal karyotype, insertions in the

genes NPM1, inv (16;9) were more often detected, while mutations in the genes t (8;21) and BRAF were more often found in patients with altered karyotype.

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